

Scaling open research information for scholarly outputs: The Data Citation Corpus advances evaluation of the impact of research data

Iratxe Puebla ^{1,2}, Maria Gould ²

¹ *Make Data Count*

² *DataCite, International Data Citation Initiative e. V, Hannover, Germany*

Background

While infrastructure and standards have been developed to collect article citations and usage metrics, getting a similar picture of the connections between journal publications and other research outputs has so far been challenging. This has inhibited the potential for research evaluation processes to incorporate a diversity of outputs, as well as our shared understanding of how these outputs are being used, and the impact and return-on-investment of efforts in open research.

Understanding and evaluating data usage is one particular area of concern in this context. Citations to datasets provide valuable information about the use of data, and librarians, repositories and other stakeholders have worked to advance the adoption of data-citation practices. However, the processes to obtain this information are often time-consuming and laborious, and do not yield the full picture of how datasets have been used, as only a fraction of data citations are reported as structured references in articles or in the dataset metadata. In addition, some of the efforts to identify connections between articles and datasets result in data citations that remain stored in closed systems.

To respond to this challenge, Make Data Count is developing the Data Citation Corpus (1), a large open aggregate store of citations to datasets identified through diverse methodologies, that will scale the data-usage information that is openly available to the community.

Approach

The Data Citation Corpus goes beyond the data citations collected via article references and dataset metadata, to incorporate mentions to data without the need for a structured citation. A key aspect of the project is collaboration with community groups who are undertaking work to identify connections between datasets and articles. These collaborations have so far included funders (Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, Aligning Science Across Parkinson's) and infrastructure providers such as EuropePMC. By leveraging these community efforts, we have for the first time aggregated data citations collected via metadata as well as machine-learning methodologies applied to the full text of articles to extract mentions to datasets independent of whether the dataset is cited within the references. This methodology holds promise to scale the data citations that can be collected without imposing an additional burden on researchers, repositories, publishers or evaluators.

The Data Citation Corpus has so far aggregated data-article links from three sources: DataCite Event Data, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI), and Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP). The citation records in the Data Citation Corpus include the persistent identifier (a DOI or an accession number) for the dataset and the repository where it was published, the DOI for the article, as well as its journal and publisher, and, where available, additional metadata such as discipline, affiliations, or funding information. Each record designates the provenance of the citation to ensure transparency around the source of that data-article link. The store of data citations in the Data Citation Corpus is publicly available as a data file (JSON and CSV) on Zenodo (2) under a CC0 license. A dashboard at <https://corpus.datacite.org/dashboard> provides an overview of the content of the Corpus and enables users to filter according to different facets such as affiliation, repository, or journal.

Insights

The Corpus currently includes 5.2 million data citations, representing 1,700 repositories and publications in over 25,000 journals. Of the data citations, 4 million are associated with datasets with accession numbers, and 1.2 million with datasets with DOIs. The disciplinary coverage currently has a strong representation of the biomedical sciences, as the repositories included in text mining for data mentions included repositories that assign accession numbers which are well established within biomedical fields (such as genetics or structural biology). The Corpus data file has been viewed over 3,700 times and has 588 downloads as of June 2025.

The Corpus has already been used by different groups and organizations to explore the usage of datasets, either by focusing on the Corpus contents or by combining the dataset-publication links with other databases. Examples include the analytical workflows and exploration developed by the data platform ReDisiv (3), or the analyses reported at the Make Data Count Summit (4) and in the latest State of Open Data report (5). Through a collaboration with Northwestern University and the University of Colorado Boulder, we have leveraged this store of data citations to analyse the use and reach of datasets from those institutions, showcasing valuable insights for academic libraries on the temporal trends on data usage and the distribution across repositories, as well as data-intensive research areas at each university (6).

Impact and next steps

The Data Citation Corpus substantially broadens the information about usage of research data that is openly available to the community, and will be a key resource to support incorporating data as part of institutional processes (7,8). Our next steps will seek to broaden the coverage of the Corpus, through complementary approaches: 1) ingestion of additional citations from other sources, in particular to expand the disciplinary coverage of the datasets included, 2) address current metadata gaps, such as those related to affiliation and funding information, and 3) scale the number of data citations by applying machine-learning approaches to identify data mentions in the text of articles.

In addition to providing a central open store of citations to datasets, the Data Citation Corpus brings additional benefits to the community. It provides a resource where groups and institutions that are already collecting data citations can contribute those openly, and increase their visibility and value for the community. As the number of data-paper links

grows, there is a strong community interest in better understanding the nature of the relationship between the dataset and the article. To this end, we have launched a Kaggle competition calling for machine-learning models that can both identify data citations in the article text and contextualize the relationship as either primary (data generated as part of the paper) or secondary (reused or derived from a prior dataset) (9). We look forward to applying these models to enrich the records in the Data Citation Corpus in the future. More broadly, the Data Citation Corpus also opens an opportunity to evolve our approach to the scholarly resource 'citation' - instead of restricting citations to a specific structured label, we can focus on building a network of connections that better reflects the diverse outputs that researchers regularly create and interact with.

The Data Citation Corpus is making it possible to aggregate and openly share data-usage information at scale, so that it can be integrated into existing research ecosystems. As the Corpus broadens its coverage, it will be a key resource for the community to assess the impact of research data outputs, and to address current gaps in the research information that is openly available for scholarly outputs.

References

1. Puebla, I. (2023). The Global Data Citation Corpus. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2023 (WOOC), Bologna, Italy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039542>
2. DataCite, & Make Data Count. (2024). Data Citation Corpus Data File (Version v2.0) [Data set]. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11196858>
3. Mathews, I., Chandler, Z., & DeLaney, E. Analyzing the Data Citation Corpus on Redivis. <https://doi.org/10.60804/1516-E177>
4. Make Data Count. The Data Citation Corpus in practice: Perspectives from a funder and an institution. <https://doi.org/10.60804/6A1Z-RR79>
5. Hahnel, M., Smith, G., & Campbell, A. (2024). The State of Open Data 2024: Special Report Bridging policy and practice in data sharing (Version 2). Digital Science. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27337476.v2>
6. Wittenberg, J., Portenoy, J., Puebla, I., & Holmes, K. (2025). Automating data citation at scale to advance open data metrics. Association of College & Research Libraries (ACRL 2025), Minneapolis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130354>
- 7 Puebla, I., Ascoli, G. A., Blume, J., Chodacki, J., Finnell, J., Kennedy, D. N., Mair, B., Martone, M. E., Wittenberg, J., & Poline, J.-B. (2024). Ten simple rules for recognizing data and software contributions in hiring, promotion, and tenure. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 20(8), e1012296. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012296>
8. Carter, C., & Puebla, I. 'Implementing data evaluation in academia' Working Group. <https://doi.org/10.60804/OSAK-7G76>
9. Lowenberg, D., & Lin, J. (2025). Announcing Make Data Count's Kaggle Competition. Make Data Count. <https://doi.org/10.60804/ASFB-F691>